

Comprehensive Orthodontic Protocol in Cleft Lip and Palate Rehabilitation

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Abstract

Cleft lip and palate rank among the most prevalent congenital conditions worldwide, with variations observed across different races, ethnicities, and regions. Issues related to cleft lip and/or palate tend to exacerbate as individuals age. While it presents as a distinct condition, its existence can adversely affect aesthetics and functionality, impacting growth, dental health, speech, hearing, and overall appearance, leading to social and psychological challenges for both the child and their parents. The origins of cleft lip and palate are multi-factorial, including genetic factors, exposure to teratogenic substances, and nutritional deficiencies, and it can manifest as either syndromic or non-syndromic clefts. The management of cleft lip and palate involves a team of various specialists, each bringing unique perspectives to a specific case, which ultimately contributes to achieving successful treatment outcomes. While the timing and methods for each intervention are still subject to debate, the orthodontist has a vital role in pre-surgical maxillary orthopaedics, which includes aligning the maxillary segments and teeth in preparation for subsequent alveolar bone grafting and achieving optimal dental relationships. Additionally, they prepare the dentition for potential prosthetic rehabilitation or orthognathic surgery if needed. Thus, to ensure an effective treatment outcome and to refine individual techniques or variations of the treatment protocol, it is essential to have a highly skilled team of specialists from various disciplines, ideally working on a multi-centre basis.

Keywords : Cleft lip; Cleft palate; Dental care; Orthodontics

Introduction

One of the most prevalent congenital abnormalities in the craniofacial region is cleft lip and palate¹. Approximately 700 infants worldwide are born with cleft lip and/or cleft palate per day, meaning that a newborn with one of these clefts is born every two minutes². Geographical location, ethnicity, gender, and socioeconomic level all affect the occurrence of cleft lip and palate, with Asians having the highest frequency, Africans the lowest, and Caucasians having an intermediate rate³.

Although the mix of genetic and environmental variables is undeniable, the exact cause of clefts is still unknown. Epidemiology takes into account environmental influences, the prevalence of drugs, alcohol, and smoking, in addition to hereditary factors as well as the mother's consumption of folic acid. It has been noted that each race in a particular nation has a different case frequency. Although the deformity is usually

unilateral, it can also be bilateral⁴⁻⁶.

CLP is a congenital abnormality that develops during pregnancy. Palatal shelves typically converge and merge during the fifth to twelfth week of pregnancy. Clefts may appear as a result of developmental abnormalities caused by disruptions in mesenchymal and endodermal cell proliferation during embryogenesis⁷. Cleft palate and cleft lip with or without cleft palate are included in the division of clefts⁸. In addition to being restricted to the uvula, cleft palate may affect the development of soft tissues⁷. About 15% of all cleft cases have solitary cleft lip, while 40% of individuals have isolated cleft palate⁹.

Because of its ability to work in tandem with other patient treatment requirements, the job of an orthodontist has expanded over time. In the early stages of cleft patient care,

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the orthodontist can help with pre-operative maxillary orthopaedics; in the intermediate stages, they can align the maxillary segments and dentition and prepare for secondary alveolar bone grafting; and in the final stages, they can help obtain the ideal dental relationship and prepare the dentition for orthognathic surgery or prosthetic rehabilitation. Soft tissues, skeletal abnormalities, and/or dental anomalies may be linked to the orthodontic malocclusion in a patient with cleft lip and palate. In order to achieve full ortho-dontic success, the orthodontist must prioritize treatment goals for each intervention and make important decisions for orthodontic intervention at the right moment.

Interdisciplinary Team

Figure 1:Diagrammatic representation of the interdisciplinary team for CLCPpatients¹⁰

An orthodontist, an oral and maxillofacial surgeon, and a cleft surgeon make up the majority of the core team. A prosthodontist, a speech and ENT expert, and a plastic surgeon are among the other essential team members.¹⁰

Treatment Protocols in Cleft Patients

Since they are the main members of the interdisciplinary team that support the surgeon during the entire reconstructive care process, orthodontists play a crucial role in managing clefts. The orthodontist helps the cleft surgeon with preoperative maxillary and nasal orthopedics throughout infancy. The orthodontist's only responsibility during the deciduous dentition stage is to address crossbite, if required. In order to prepare for secondary alveolar bone grafting, the maxillary segments and dentition must align during the transitional dentition period. The orthodontist's job is to achieve good dental and occlusal interactions during the permanent dentition and late adolescence. They also have to get the dentition ready for orthognathic surgery and prosthetic rehabilitation, if necessary.¹¹

This is summarized in the table given below

Stage	Treatment
Infancy	Presurgical nasal and maxillary orthopedics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeding devices • Pre-surgical orthopedics • Nasoalveolar moulding • Primary Lip Surgery • Cleft Palate Surgery • Velopharyngeal Dysfunction & its treatment
Deciduous Dentition	Crossbite Correction (if necessary)
Transitional Dentition	Maxillary Expansion Intrusion of Premaxilla Maxillary Protraction Alveolar bone grafting
Permanent Dentition	Comprehensive Orthodontic Treatment Distraction Osteogenesis Orthognathic Surgery

Infancy

The maxillary arch is invariably deformed in infants with cleft lip and palate. The pre-maxillary segment is typically shifted anteriorly and the posterior segments are folded lingually in patients with bilateral cleft lip and palate. People with unilateral cleft lip and palate typically have less severe deformities.¹²

Feeding Devices

Because they are unable to achieve a satisfactory seal of the oral cavity, children born with cleft lip and palate frequently exhibit eating issues. Choking and nasal regurgitation are frequent issues that arise from the palate's incapacity to distinguish between the nasal and oral chambers. For the feeding plate, Agarwal A et al.¹³ employed ethylene vinyl acetate and floss in a patient who had a unilateral cleft lip and palate. Using ethylene vinyl acetate instead of acrylic had the advantage of producing a softer, smoother surface without the need for retentive wire.

A floss was used because it prevents swallowing and helps in early retrieval of the appliance. Once the appliance was placed in the oral cavity, the child could be easily fed.

Presurgical Orthopedics

Early in the 1950s, Mc Neil proposed the idea of presurgical orthopedics. Neonatal orthopaedics, according to Mc Neil, may change the maxilla's postnatal growth by promoting the development of soft tissues that cover the hard palate. The initial idea was to form a butt joint between the cleft's alveolar segments. Presurgical orthopedics helps with speech development, normalizes tongue position, and creates a good working plate. Pre-

surgical orthopaedics is also anticipated to improve the patient's psychological well being and nose and cleft maxilla symmetry.

Nasoalveolar Moulding

A method for simultaneously correcting the nose, lip, and alveoli was disclosed by Gralson et al.¹⁴. This is completed in the initial weeks following delivery. A tiny piece of tape is applied across the baby's face, and a specially designed molding plate that resembles an orthodontic retainer is affixed. The apparatus consists of a stiff wire connecting an acrylic bulb (nasal stent) to the maxillary plate. The nasal dome is raised by the bulb, which also shapes the soft tissue of the cleft area and the nostrils. Active molding and passive growth guidance are used to mold alveoli. The interdisciplinary cleft team typically evaluates NAM 1-2 weeks after delivery, and it must be activated and changed weekly. This is beneficial to approximate the cleft segments and reduce the cleft gap.

Advantages of NAM

By reducing the cleft side alar curvature and lengthening the columella, this therapy helps the patient. It also improves the surgical aesthetics by making the prolabium more visible through the premaxilla's retractions.

NAM Protocol

Visit	Procedure
First visit (Birth - 2 weeks)	Parent Counselling Feeding instructions Lip taping only
Second visit	Impressions for NAM plate Lip taping
Third visit	Delivery of NAM plate Lip taping
Subsequent visit (every 2 weeks)	NAM plate adjustment Lip taping

Primary Lip Surgery

Repairing a cleft lip is often done about 10 weeks of age. This enables a thorough medical assessment of the patient in order to identify any congenital abnormalities that may be affecting other organ systems. The rule of ten states that lip repair should be postponed until the infant is at least 10 weeks old, weighs 10 pounds, and has a hemoglobin level of at least 10 dL/mg. The major goal of primary surgery is to achieve a functional lip that can produce a healthy lip seal while also improving the appearance of the lip, prolabium, and columella.

There are two common techniques for primary lip closure:

1. Millard's rotation flap
2. Randall Tension's triangular flap procedure

Cleft Palate Surgery

Repairing a cleft palate typically takes place between the ages of 9 and 18 month. Closing oronasal communication, which

involves the hard and soft palate, and anatomic repair of the musculature which is necessary for appropriate speech are the two primary objectives of cleft palate surgery during infancy. Numerous methods for palate repair have been documented.

The commonly used techniques include:

1. Bardach two flap palatoplasty
2. von Lange back palatoplasty

Pushback procedures are not preferred since they do not improve speech, limit growth, and increase palatal scarring.

Velopharyngeal Dysfunction

Unwanted communication between the nasal and mouth canals leads to velopharyngeal dysfunction. Giving the child an oronasal structure that promotes proper speech and resonance is the main goal of palate restoration. To keep the nasal and oral cavities apart, the palate must be closed.

All oral sounds must be produced with the velopharyngeal valve closed completely and firmly for normal speaking. Velopharyngeal insufficiency (VPI), which is defined as inadequate closure of the velopharyngeal valve due to an irregularity of the anatomy, is the biggest issue for children with cleft palate.

Treatment of Velopharyngeal Dysfunction involves a secondary surgical procedure or the use of a pharyngeal obturator.

Deciduous Dentition

The eruption of primary teeth near an alveolar deficiency may be delayed in children with an alveolar cleft defect. It is possible for the primary lateral incisor to be congenitally absent or deformed. In addition, the primary dentition grows similarly to children without clefts. The dentition frequently reflects the underlying skeletal difference, even though the distribution of the young child's adipose tissue and soft tissue draping conceals the midface's developing skeletal insufficiency in children with clefts. There may be bilateral or unilateral anterior and/or posterior cross bites. The crossbite may be linked to a functional shift, such as a slip from centric relation to centric occlusion. In certain instances, the issue may be resolved by equilibration, which eliminates occlusal interference.

Orthodontic tooth movement could be required in other situations. It was thought that, even if it is conceivable, orthodontic therapy in the primary teeth is not recommended¹⁵. Detachable appliances may not be able to be used at this point due to limited patient participation, and the possibility of lengthy treatment makes this strategy inappropriate.

Mixed Dentition

Maxillary Expansion

About 21% of children have some kind of transverse skeletal discrepancy involving the dental arches, according to a research by Silva et al. (2007). Therefore, enlargement is necessary in the majority of cleft instances.¹⁶ Patients with cleft lip and palate are frequently treated with the following expansion devices:

- Alternate Rapid Maxillary Expansion and Constriction (Eric Liou, 2005): Fan shaped expander that aids in the growth of a

hypoplastic maxilla

- NiTi palatal expander (Arndt WV, 1993): Uses super elastic and shape memory of nickel titanium wires
- Hyrax Expander (Biederman, 1968): Comfortable, hygienic, and prevents lesions to the oral mucosa
- Quad Helix (Ricketts, 1978): A slow expander that offers asymmetrical expansion in both the anterior and transverse directions

Intrusion of Premaxilla

One of the most prevalent abnormalities in patients with bilateral cleft lip and palate in primary and mixed dentition is a large and downward displaced premaxilla. Numerous studies have shown that the premaxilla's prominence gradually diminishes and disappears during the growing phase. As a result, several experts advise against treating pre-maxillary abnormalities until adulthood. But if these abnormalities are not corrected until adulthood, it could make alveolar bone grafting more difficult and have a psychological effect on the young patients. For the orthopedic intrusion of the premaxilla, Liou et al.¹⁷ created an intraoral tooth borne distraction device that applies a strong, sporadic force. The extension arm and screw pivot around the hinge when the screw is twisted clockwise, and the hinged bolt moves upward and somewhat rearward generating intrusive force.

Figure 3: Intraoral distraction device for intrusion of premaxilla - Liou et al¹⁷

Maxillary Protraction

Patients with cleft lip and palate frequently have maxillary hypoplasia. In moderate situations of Class III malocclusion, facemask therapy or protraction headgear (PHG) can be used non-surgically to encourage sutural growth at the circum-maxillary sutures in developing patients.

Facemask therapy's primary drawbacks are clockwise mandibular rotation, non-compliance, and dentoalveolar compensation.¹⁸ A labiolingual arch, quad helix, and fast maxillary expansion are examples of intraoral devices that have been employed to transfer the orthopedic force from the protraction facemask to the maxilla.¹⁰ By transferring orthopedic force directly to circum-maxillary sutures, a novel approach known as Bone Anchored Maxillary Protraction¹⁹ removes the necessity for an extraoral facemask and permits the use of intermaxillary traction 24 hours per day.

Alveolar Bone Grafting (ABG)

More than a century ago, in 1914, Drachter reported the first successful alveolar bone graft. Its goal is to give the cleft in the alveolus region a bone bridge. When ABG is successful, the maxillary arch is stabilized, there is enough bone for periodontal health and tooth support, the piriform rim architecture is normalized, nasal aesthetics are improved, and speech parameters are improved. An ineffective ABG, on the other hand, may result in tooth loss, ongoing nasal regurgitation, nasal air emission, and jeopardize subsequent orthodontic and orthognathic therapy.²⁰ Since extra surgery is necessary to harvest bone at a relatively young age, primary and early secondary bone grafting is no longer practiced.

The maxilla may have more growth abnormalities as a result of these procedures. Boyne and Sands introduced secondary bone grafting in 1972. Grafted cancellous bone from the iliac crest is used to bridge the cleft segment; after an average of three months, the bone becomes unidentifiable in radiographic images.

Permanent Dentition

Comprehensive Orthodontic Treatment

Usually, between the ages of 10 and 15, patients will come in for extensive orthodontic treatment. The procedure is delayed until the permanent teeth have emerged and all of the primary teeth have exfoliated. Treatment for patients with cleft lip and palate, however, may begin earlier; that is, two to three years after secondary bone grafting, when the permanent canines have erupted.

Based on the maxilla's negative overjet and deficit, the case is evaluated for orthodontic therapy or, alternatively, orthodontic treatment in conjunction with orthognathic surgery.²¹ Fixed appliances are used to complete the orthodontic therapy. This aids in proper arch alignment and the treatment of dental malpositions. Every effort should be made to preserve the lateral incisor if it is located in a cleft location. If the lateral incisor is absent, the gap can be preserved for prosthetic rehabilitation or it can be closed with orthodontic therapy.

Orthognathic Surgery

In order to achieve good aesthetics and stable dental occlusion, patients with significant maxillomandibular basal jaw discrepancies and unfavorable growth patterns need orthodontics and orthognathic surgical treatment. Typically, a Le Fort I osteotomy is performed to advance the mandible, either alone or in conjunction with BSSO (Bilateral Sagittal Split Osteotomy) for the reduction of mandibular length.

Soft tissue infection, bone necrosis, tooth loss, and delayed recovery make cleft orthognathic surgery extremely challenging. Scarring from prior surgery and vascularity impairment are the main causes of these problems. Due to the forward motion of the soft palate and the advancement of the maxilla, patients with palatal clefts are at risk of developing deteriorating velopharyngeal insufficiency (increased hypernasality of the voice). As a

result, the speech pathologist must always perform a pre-operative evaluation. For these people, distraction osteogenesis is a good alternative.²²

Distraction Osteogenesis

Distraction Osteogenesis is the process of separating the two sides of a bone to create new bone after an osteotomy or corticotomy. Distraction osteogenesis, which was first discovered for orthopaedic surgery, is now recommended as a successful treatment method for a number of craniofacial abnormalities. It makes it possible for the surrounding soft tissue envelope to expand concurrently with the progressive bone production, improving the reconstruction's long-term stability and lowering the chance of recurrence.²³

Distraction osteogenesis can be carried out with the help of an external or internal distractor. The steps involved include:²³

1. Osteotomy and placement of the distraction device
2. Latency period (Callus organisation)
3. Distraction (time when gradual traction is applied and distraction regenerate is formed). Gradual distraction is carried out at 0.5-1mm per day
4. Consolidation (allows maturation and corticalization of the regenerate after traction forces are discontinued)

Conclusion

Treatment for a child with cleft lip and palate starts the moment of birth. Many dentists find treating patients with clefts to be difficult, time consuming, and expensive. For the patient to receive high quality care and benefit, a thorough evaluation of the youngster is required.

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